

Photochemical intramolecular cyclization routes to heterocycles[†]

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1-Aryl-3-(2-azidoaryl)prop-2-en-1-ones have been prepared from *o*-nitro aromatic aldehydes. The 2-aryloindole derivatives are easily prepared from these derivatives in a tandem reaction sequence in moderate yields. Photolytic process is found to be much more facile than the thermal process in this transformation. Naphthofuran derivatives have been prepared by metal-catalyzed intramolecular photocyclizations of 1-aryl-3-(2-methoxy-1-naphthyl)- and 1-aryl-3-(1-methoxy-2-naphthyl)prop-2-en-1-ones.

Amongst different heterocycles, a major impetus for research on indole derivatives (**1**) has stemmed from the significant physiological function of this ring system. Besides the pharmacologically active ergot alkaloids, several synthetic derivatives of indole-like vincristine, vinblastine and many others are also known to show antihypertensive, anti-inflammatory and tranquilizing activity. Many procedures are known for preparing the indoles¹, and availability of starting material as well as compatibility with reaction conditions play vital roles in choosing the proper procedure. Besides the commonly used methods like Fischer indole synthesis¹, Batcho-Leimgruber synthetic method involving *o*-nitrotoluene and dimethylformamide acetal^{1,2} and the Gassman indole synthesis from *N*-haloanilines¹. Transition metals have also been used in the synthesis of indoles³⁻⁶ and aromatic nitro compounds can be deoxygenated with trivalent phosphorous compounds to give indole deriva-

Recently, a three-step sequence has been reported for converting *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde into 2-nitroindole in moderate yield by thermolysis of 2-(*o*-azidophenyl)nitroethylene¹². Since azides on photolysis is expected to give the nitrene intermediates efficiently which may be used for ready intramolecular cyclization to indole derivatives, we explored this sequence for the syntheses of 2-aryloindole compounds **1** and **2** from the corresponding 2-azidobenzaldehyde derivatives **3** and 1-azidonaphthaldehyde **4**.

Following the Spagnolo procedure¹³ the corresponding aromatic nitroaldehydes were treated with sodium azide in HMPA at room temperature to give these 2-azidobenzaldehydes in quantitative yields. Aldol condensation of the azidoaldehyde with substituted acetophenone followed by dehydration of the resulting keto-alcohols at ambient temperature gave colored crystals of the 1-aryl-3-(2-azidoaryl)prop-2-en-1-ones (**5a-f**, Table 1).

tives⁷. This latter procedure has been used for preparing 2-acyl and 2-aryl derivatives of indole in small amount (16%). Photolysis or thermolysis of vinylazides followed by intramolecular cyclization of the electrophilic nitrene across a double bond can be used for 2- or 3-substituted indoles⁸⁻¹¹. Non-availability of suitable starting material probably deterred the use of this method for the synthesis of 2-aryloindoles.

Table 1. Characteristics of 1-aryl-3-(2-azidoaryl)prop-2-en-1-ones (**5a-f**), **7**

Comd. no.	Color	Yield(%)	M.p. (°C)	$\nu_{N-N=N}$ (cm ⁻¹)
5a	Blue	60	55	2125
5b	Red	65	60	2130
5c	Red	75	62	2120
5d	Red	75	96	2120
5e	Green	80	114	2120
5f	Yellow	64	136	2120
7	Yellow	70	128	2110

On photolysis, vinyl azides normally lose nitrogen with the formation of 2*H*-azirines. The azirine then may undergo reversible carbon-nitrogen bond cleavage to give the corresponding vinyl nitrene¹⁴. In our case, the azides **5a-f** on irradiation in methanol for 1.5 h are then likely to produce the corresponding nitrenes with the elimination of nitrogen.

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Scheme 1

A tandem intramolecular electrocyclic ring closure of the nitrene then led to a non-aromatic fused 2*H*-pyrrole (6a-f) which was then followed by a [1,5]-hydrogen shift from carbon to nitrogen in 6a-f to give the 2-aryloxy derivatives of indole 1a-f in moderate yields (Table 2). In 1*H*-indene the migratory aptitude of an acyl group is reported to be more than hydrogen¹⁵. On the other hand, in heterocyclic series like indole, an extra driving force of aromatization appears to be responsible for the faster migration of hydrogen than the aryl group¹⁶.

In a comparative study when the azidochalcone derivative 5c was refluxed in toluene, it took a much longer time (16 h) for the similar reaction sequence to take place giving the corresponding indole derivative 1c in 64% yield.

Following a similar process, yellow crystals of 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-(1-azido-2-naphthyl)prop-2-en-1-one (7)

Table 2. Characteristics of the aryloxyindole derivatives 1a-f and 2

Comd. no.	M.p. (°C) (yield, %)	ν_{N-H} cm ⁻¹	λ_{max} , nm (log ϵ)	δ (N-H) ppm
1a ^a	148 (57)	3315	248 (4.2), 324 (4.3)	9.32
1b	162 (60)	3310	256 (4.5), 324 (4.3)	9.37
1c	185 (68)	3330	326 (4.2)	9.38
1d	190 (75)	3310	258 (4.1), 326 (4.3)	9.46
1e	165 (73)	3310	218 (4.7), 252 (4.4), 294 (4.0), 328 (4.3)	9.34
1f	198 (60)	3280	218 (4.8), 252 (4.4), 286 (4.1), 369 (4.4)	9.73
2	202 (65)	3280	246 (4.4), 253 (4.4), 290 (4.1), 336 (4.3)	10.41

^aRef. 7.

was obtained from 4 in 70% yield which on irradiation for 1.5 h underwent this tandem reaction sequence to give the 2-aryloxyindole 2 in 65% yield.

We have observed similar intramolecular *ortho*-photocyclization of methoxynaphthyl analog of chalcone to give naphtho[2,1-*b*]- (8) and naphtho[1,2-*b*]furans (9)¹⁷. Although metal-catalyzed photocyclization of vinyl arenes is not common in the literature, in these cases irradiation with 450 W medium pressure mercury lamp in presence of Cu^{II} gave good yields of the naphthofurans^{17a}. Since the absorption spectra of these molecules did not show any

Ar = C₆H₅; 4-OMe-C₆H₄; 4-Me-C₆H₄;
2-OMe-4-Me-C₆H₃; 2,4-diOMe-C₆H₃;

Ar = 4-OMe-C₆H₄;
4-Me-C₆H₄

4-Cl-C₆H₄; 2-naphthyl

charge-transfer band in the presence of Cu^{II}, its catalytic influence appeared to be operative only in the photoexcited state of such molecules (A). Interestingly, oxygen has been found to facilitate the reaction. While presence of oxygen may help autogeneration of the catalyst, absence of any retarding effect in its presence suggests involvement of a reactive singlet state in this photoreaction. The reactive excited state of an enone has generally been assumed to be a charge polarized n, π^* state with higher electron density at C _{β} than at C _{α} ¹⁸. A similar characteristic was expected in the excited state of molecules of type A (Scheme 2) where a charge polarized excited enone part of A* may then by electron transfer to Cu^{II} give an organocopper intermediate which may then undergo a tandem photocyclization followed by H-elimination giving the naphthofuran derivatives^{17a}.

This metal catalyzed photocyclization has been found to be dependent on the nature of the metal salts used. Thus, from A (Ar = *p*-OMe-C₆H₄) the naphthofuran was obtained in comparable yield with Cu^I as well as with Mn^{II} salts but the yield was much less (26%) with Ni^{II}, whereas Cd^{II} did not initiate any photocyclization. Since an ionic product formation on photolysis has been reported to be dependent on the metal salt used¹⁹, the observed dependence of photocyclization on metal salts is thus expected in these cases. Furthermore, benzofurans could not be prepared following this process. Thus while electron transfer to the metal ion appeared to be a favorable process for the methoxy-naphthyl analog of chalcone, that for the chalcone derivatives appeared to be an unfavorable one.

Scheme 2

Experimental

2-Azido-1-naphthaldehyde and 2-azido-1-benzaldehyde were prepared from the 2-nitro-1-naphthaldehyde and 2-nitro-1-benzaldehyde by reported procedure^{13,20}. The naphthofuran derivatives of **8** and **9** using Cu^{II} catalyst were prepared by a reported procedure¹⁷.

1-Aryl-3-(2-azidoaryl)prop-2-en-1-ones. General procedure :

To a 0° cooled solution of 2-azidoarylaldehyde (6 mmol) and substituted acetophenone (6 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml), a solution of KOH (6 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. After stirring for 2–3 h at room temperature, the reaction mixture was acidified with dil. HCl and poured into ice-cold water (100 ml). The resulting precipitate was washed with water till free from acid and then dried and crystallized from methanol to give crystals of 1-aryl-3-(2-azidoaryl)prop-2-en-1-ones. Since azides are prone to explosion, their analyses were not performed.

1-Phenyl-3-(2-azidophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (5a) : from acetophenone, ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 7.16–7.26 (2H, m), 7.41–7.62 (6H, m), 7.70 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.98–8.039 (2H, m). *1-(4-Methylphenyl)-3-(2-azidophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (5b)* : from (4-methyl)acetophenone, ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 2.44 (3H, s, Me), 7.15–7.26 (2H, m), 7.30 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.43 (1H, t), 7.56 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 7.69 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.99 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz). *1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-(2-azidophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (5c)* : from (4-methoxy)acetophenone, ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 3.89 (3H, s), 6.97 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.15–7.25 (2H, m), 7.39–7.45 (1H, m), 7.56 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), 7.67–7.69 (1H, m), 7.95–8.05 (3H, m). *1-(4-Bromophenyl)-3-(2-azidophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (5d)* : from (4-bromo)acetophenone, ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 7.21–7.31 (2H, m), 7.48 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 7.68–7.75 (3H, m), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 8.05 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz). *1-(2-Naphthyl)-3-(2-azidophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (5e)* : from methyl 2-naphthylketone, ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 7.16–7.23 (2H, m), 7.40–7.45 (1H, m), 7.52–7.76 (4H, m), 7.86–8.08

(5H, m), 8.5 (1H, s). *1-(2-Naphthyl)-3-(4,5-dimethoxy-2-azidophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (5f)* : from methyl 2-naphthylketone, ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 4.0 (3H, s), 4.06 (3H, s), 7.09 (1H, s), 7.28 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz), 7.60–7.63 (3H, m), 7.89–8.09 (4H, m), 8.26 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz), 8.59 (1H, s). *1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-(1-azidonaphth-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one* : from 2-azido-1-naphthaldehyde and (4-methoxy)acetophenone, ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 3.8 (3H, s, OMe), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.56–7.62 (3H, m), 7.68–7.75 (2H, m), 7.82–7.85 (1H, m), 8.06 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 8.19–8.22 (1H, m), 8.34 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz).

Irradiation of the azide derivatives 5a-f and 7. General procedure :

The azide derivatives (0.5 mmol) were dissolved in dry methanol (170 ml). The solutions were irradiated in a pyrex vessel using Hanovia 450 W medium pressure mercury lamp under argon atmosphere for 1.5 h (monitored by tlc). After the reactions were completed, the solvents were removed *in vacuo* and the residual masses were subjected to chromatography over silica gel column. The indole derivatives were obtained by eluting with 40% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether and crystallized from chloroform/petroleum ether (1 : 3) to give white crystals of the indoles **1a-f** and **2**. *1a* from **5a** : ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 7.17 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.31–7.42 (1H, m), 7.44–7.65 (4H, m), 7.72 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.95–8.00 (2H, m), 9.32 (1H, b s). *1b* from **5b** : (Found : C, 82.18; H, 5.40; N, 5.93. C₁₆H₁₃ON calcd. for : C, 81.67; H, 5.56; N, 5.95%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 2.46 (3H, s, Me), 7.16 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.32–7.43 (3H, m), 7.47 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.72 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 9.37 (1H, b s), ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) δ 21.7, 112.2, 112.4, 121.0, 123.2, 126.4, 127.8, 129.2, 129.4, 134.5, 135.3, 137.5, 143.2, 187.0. *1c* from **5c** : (Found : C, 76.27; H, 5.11; N, 5.53. C₁₆H₁₃O₂N calcd. for : C, 76.47; H, 5.21; N, 5.57%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 3.92 (3H, s), 7.03 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.14–7.19 (2H, m), 7.34–7.39 (1H, m), 7.48 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.72 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 8.04 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 9.38 (1H, b s), ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) δ 55.5, 111.9, 112.2, 113.7, 113.8, 120.9, 123.1, 126.2, 127.8, 130.6, 131.6, 132.3, 134.5, 137.3, 163.2, 185.9. *1d* from **5d** : (Found : C, 60.11; H, 3.42; N, 4.41. C₁₅H₁₀ONBr calcd. for : C, 60.02; H, 3.35; N, 4.66%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 7.14–7.20 (2H, m), 7.36–7.4 (1H, m), 7.48 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.68 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.72 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.87 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 9.46 (1H, b s), ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) δ 112.2, 112.8, 121.2, 123.2, 126.7, 127.3, 127.6, 130.7, 131.7, 133.9, 136.6, 137.6, 185.9. *1e* from **5e** : (Found : C, 84.01; H, 5.06; N, 5.14. C₁₉H₁₃ON calcd. for : C, 84.11; H, 4.82; N, 5.16%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 7.19 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.40 (1H, t), 7.51 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz),

7.57–7.66 (2H, m), 7.75 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 7.92–8.06 (5H, m), 8.55 (1H, s), 9.34 (1H, b s), ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz) δ 112.1, 112.7, 121.0, 123.2, 125.2, 126.5, 126.8, 127.5, 127.7, 127.8, 128.1, 128.4, 129.3, 130.5, 131.0, 184.8. **1f** from **5f**: (Found: C, 75.66; H, 4.93; N, 4.03. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ calcd. for: C, 76.11; H, 5.19; N, 4.22%); ^1H NMR (300 MHz) δ 3.93 (3H, s), 3.96 (3H, s), 6.94 (1H, s), 7.07 (1H, s), 7.15 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz), 7.56–7.65 (2H, m), 7.92–8.03 (3H, m), 8.52 (1H, s), 9.73 (1H, s). **2** from **7**: (Found: C, 79.37; H, 5.02; N, 4.53. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ calcd. for: C, 79.71; H, 5.01; N, 4.64%); ^1H NMR (300 MHz) δ 3.93 (3H, s), 7.06 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.29 (1H, s), 7.51–7.60 (3H, m), 7.69 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 7.92 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 8.09 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 8.28 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 10.41 (1H, b s), ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz) δ 55.5, 113.6, 113.8, 121.4, 121.4, 121.9, 122.3, 124.2, 126.0, 126.1, 128.8, 130.9, 131.6, 132.4, 133.4, 134.0, 163.1, 185.6.

Irradiation of 1-(4-methoxy-1-phenyl)-3-(2-methoxy-1-naphthyl)prop-2-en-1-one (A) in presence of different metal salts:

In presence of Cu^{II} salts: A mixture of compound **A** (318 mg, 1 mmol) and copper(II) acetate (140 mg, 0.55 mmol) dissolved in dry methanol (170 ml) was irradiated in a pyrex vessel using Hanovia 450 W lamp for 1.5 h. The solvent was then removed *in vacuo* and the residual mass was chromatographed over a silica gel column. Elution of the column with 20% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether gave white crystals (193 mg, 64%) of **8** (Ar = 4-methoxy-1-phenyl), m.p. 158° (lit.¹⁷ 158°).

In presence of Cu^{I} salt: The above procedure was repeated with **A** (318 mg, 1 mmol) and copper(I) acetonitrile perchlorate (110 mg, 0.54 mmol) for 2 h to give **8** (Ar = 4-methoxy-1-phenyl) (230 mg, 75%), m.p. 158° (m.m.p. 158°).

In presence of Mn^{III} salt: The above procedure was repeated with **A** (200 mg, 0.63 mmol) and $\text{Mn}(\text{OAc})_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (166 mg, 0.62 mmol) for 3 h to give **8** (Ar = 4-methoxy-1-phenyl) (230 mg, 75%), m.p. 158° (m.m.p. 158°).

In presence of Ni^{II} salt: The above procedure was repeated with **A** (200 mg, 0.63 mmol) and $\text{Ni}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (156 mg, 0.63 mmol) for 3 h to give **8** (Ar = 4-methoxy-1-phenyl) (50 mg, 26%), m.p. 158° (m.m.p. 158°).

In presence of Cd^{II} salt: The above procedure was repeated with **A** (200 mg, 0.63 mmol) and $\text{Cd}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

(168 mg, 0.63 mmol) for 6 h to give a tarry complex residue with no trace of **8** (Ar = 4-methoxy-1-phenyl).

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